

Strengthening Democratic Governance in India through Electoral Reforms

Paper Id : 21292 Submission Date : 2022-07-12 Acceptance Date : 2022-07-21 Publication Date : 2022-07-25
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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.19004164

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Abstract

Elections are a fundamental element of democratic governance. However, the electoral process in India continues to face significant structural and procedural challenges. Persistent concerns include the influence of money power, criminalization of politics, electoral violence, booth capturing, communal mobilization, and the proliferation of non-serious or proxy candidates. These challenges underscore the necessity for comprehensive electoral reforms to enhance both representative legitimacy and institutional integrity. This study examines the causes of distortions within India's electoral framework and proposes corrective measures to strengthen democratic governance. It critically evaluates the role of institutions such as the Election Commission of India in ensuring free and fair elections, while identifying legal and administrative constraints that limit their effectiveness. The paper further analyses previous reform initiatives including candidate disclosure requirements, electronic voting mechanisms, and campaign finance regulations, to assess their impact and identify persisting gaps. Drawing upon constitutional provisions, judicial pronouncements, and comparative democratic practices, the study advances policy-oriented recommendations aimed at improving transparency, accountability, voter participation, and institutional autonomy. It concludes that sustained institutional commitment, legal innovation, and active civic engagement are essential for safeguarding the credibility and effectiveness of India's electoral democracy.

Keywords Accountability, Administrative Foundations, Criminalization, Demagogue, Democratic Institutions, Law Commission, Transparency.

Introduction

Elections and Democracy in India

Elections are often regarded as emblematic of the full establishment of democratic governance, and accordingly significant importance is attached to their timely conduct. However, it is not the mere occurrence of elections, but rather their character and quality, that truly signify progress toward democratic consolidation. Elections constitute the institutional foundation of democratic governance in India, where periodic and competitive polls enable citizens to participate directly in the selection of their representatives. Since the first general elections of 1951-52, conducted under the supervision of the Election Commission of India, elections have played a crucial role in sustaining constitutional values such as popular sovereignty, political equality, and accountability. As Sukumar Sen observed, India's first general election was an "act of faith," underscoring the formidable challenge of organizing nationwide polls under universal adult franchise immediately after

independence from colonial rule. In light of the country's vast geographical expanse and its complex political and social diversity, the electoral process requires continual refinement; accordingly, sustained and systematic electoral reforms are essential for the effective consolidation of India's democratic system. They facilitate peaceful transfers of power, provide legitimacy to governments, and create channels through which diverse social groups, including historically marginalized communities, can articulate their interests within the democratic framework. The effective functioning of democracy depends upon public confidence that elections are conducted freely and fairly, without manipulation, and that they serve as genuine instruments for representing citizens' preferences rather than ritualistic exercises designed merely to create an appearance of choice. At the same time, persistent challenges such as money power, criminalization of politics, identity-based mobilization, and declining public trust underscore the need for continuous electoral reforms to strengthen transparency and fairness. Thus, while elections remain the lifeblood of India's democracy, their effectiveness depends on institutional integrity, informed voter participation, and sustained commitment to constitutional ideals. However, elections in India are often not conducted under ideal conditions owing to the pervasive influence of excessive campaign expenditure and the deployment of muscle power. Although the first three general elections were largely considered free and fair, a perceptible decline in electoral standards became evident from the fourth general election in 1967 and intensified in subsequent decades. The electoral system of India is marked by many problems that have encouraged anti-social elements to jump into the electoral fray. Over time, the electoral system has exhibited serious infirmities that have contributed to the entrenchment of political corruption and the erosion of ethical norms in public life. In many instances, candidates and political parties pursue electoral victory at any cost, disregarding principles of integrity and public service. Ideally, a democratic electoral process should enable honest and public-spirited individuals to contest elections and represent the people.

Objective of study

This study examines the causes of distortions within India's electoral framework and proposes corrective measures to strengthen democratic governance. It critically evaluates the role of institutions such as the Election Commission of India in ensuring free and fair elections, while identifying legal and administrative constraints that limit their effectiveness.

Review of Literature

The paper is based on various reviews of books, online literature and online sources available which is discussed throughout the paper.

Analysis**Committees for Electoral Reforms**

Electoral reform in India has long attracted extensive scholarly attention but relatively limited implementation. Numerous committees and expert bodies have examined the issue in depth and produced a wide array of recommendations aimed at ensuring free and fair elections under the supervision of the Election Commission of India. Yet, a survey of these reform proposals reveals a persistent gap between normative recommendations and their practical realization, reflecting institutional inertia and political reluctance. A historical perspective further demonstrates that contemporary debates on electoral reform do not arise in isolation; rather, they build upon a substantial legacy of earlier deliberations and proposals that have sought to make India's electoral democracy more representative, transparent, and effective within the constitutional framework established by the Constitution of India. Recognizing this continuity underscores both the enduring relevance of electoral reform and the necessity of sustained political commitment to translate well-considered proposals into meaningful institutional change. A number of remedies have been proposed by the various committees on electoral reforms in India.

Jayaprakash Narayan had set up, on behalf of the Citizens for Democracy, a Committee on Electoral Reforms under the chairmanship of V. M. Tarkunde in 1974. Although the committee submitted its report in 1975, Just before the national emergency, its significance lay not merely in chronology but in the comprehensive and foundational nature of its recommendations, which subsequently informed the work of later reform bodies. The Tarkunde Committee emphasized that the Election Commission of India must

be not only impartial in fact but also perceived to be so in public confidence. To this end, it proposed that members of the Commission be appointed by the President on the advice of a collegium comprising the Prime Minister, the Leader of the Opposition in the Lok Sabha (or a member of Parliament selected by the opposition), and the Chief Justice of India. The committee further recommended the appointment of regional or state election commissioners, either for individual states or for clusters of contiguous states, endowed with authority during elections to appoint election, returning, and polling officers across constituencies. It also envisaged these offices as permanent institutions responsible for continuous tasks such as periodic revision of electoral rolls and the maintenance of election records, thereby strengthening the administrative foundations of India's electoral system.

The Report of the Tarkunde Committee was published in February 1975, received wide appreciation across the country for its comprehensive and forward-looking recommendations. However, the declaration of the Emergency soon thereafter interrupted meaningful deliberation and effectively stalled the implementation of its proposals. Following the restoration of democratic processes, and acting upon a suggestion made by Jayaprakash Narayan, the National Executive Council of Citizens for Democracy resolved, at its meeting held on 13 August 1977, to constitute a Committee on Election Expenses. This initiative reflected a renewed commitment within civil society to address concerns relating to escalating campaign expenditure and to advance the broader agenda of electoral reform in post-Emergency India.

The Dinesh Goswami Committee on Electoral Reforms laid particular emphasis on safeguarding the institutional independence of the Election Commission of India. In this regard, it recommended that the protection of salary, tenure, and other service conditions of the Chief Election Commissioner and the Election Commissioners should be expressly secured through constitutional provisions. Drawing an analogy with the safeguards available to the Chief Justice and Judges of the Supreme Court of India, the Committee argued that similar constitutional protection was necessary to insulate the Commission from executive interference and to reinforce its autonomy and credibility within the electoral framework.

The Vohra Committee was constituted by the Government of India in 1993, highlighted in unequivocal terms the deepening nexus between criminal syndicates and sections of the political class. Drawing upon reports submitted by agencies such as the Central Bureau of Investigation, the Committee observed that organized crime networks in many parts of the country had begun to operate with impunity, exercising significant influence even in smaller urban and rural areas. In extreme cases, these networks were described as functioning like parallel authorities, undermining the rule of law and eroding democratic governance. The Committee therefore emphasized the urgent need for institutional safeguards to prevent the criminalization of politics and to protect the integrity of electoral and political processes in India.

The Indrajit Gupta Committee on State Funding of Elections, constituted on 3 June 1998, focused primarily on the critical issue of election financing. Following an all-party meeting on 22 May 1998 convened to deliberate on comprehensive electoral reforms, the Committee submitted its report on 30 December 1998. It unequivocally argued that state funding of elections was the most effective means of curbing the undue influence of money power on the democratic mandate. According to the Committee, such funding was both constitutionally and legally justified, though it should initially be limited to political parties recognized as national or state parties by the Election Commission of India. The Committee recommended that, at the outset, only a portion of political parties' financial requirements be borne by the state, with the possibility of gradually increasing support so that legitimate campaign expenses might ultimately become a public charge. Importantly, it proposed that state assistance be provided in kind, such as free airtime on public media, subsidized campaign materials, and other logistical support, rather than in cash, in order to ensure accountability and minimize misuse.

Judicial verdicts and electoral reforms

Judicial verdicts have played a decisive role in shaping electoral reforms in India by advancing transparency, accountability, and voter choice through constitutional interpretation. In *Union of India v. Association for Democratic Reforms*, the Supreme

Court of India laid down seminal guidelines significantly advancing transparency in the electoral process. Exercising the plenary powers of the Election Commission of India under Article 324 of the Constitution of India, the Court directed that every candidate contesting elections to Parliament or a State Legislature must furnish, on affidavit and as part of the nomination process, detailed information concerning specific aspects of their background. First, these disclosures include that whether the candidate has been convicted, acquitted, or charged in any criminal case, including details of punishment by imprisonment or fine. Second, that whether, within six months prior to filing nomination, the candidate has been accused in any pending case involving an offence punishable with imprisonment of two years or more, where charges have been framed or cognizance taken by a competent court. Third, include the movable and immovable assets, bank balances, other financial holdings of the candidate, as well as those of their spouse and dependents. Fourth was financial liabilities, particularly outstanding dues to public financial institutions or government bodies. And fifth that the candidate's educational qualifications. The Court recognized that such information serves a vital public purpose by enabling citizens to make informed electoral choices and by promoting probity in public life. By mandating disclosure of criminal antecedents, financial status, and educational background, the judgment marked a transformative moment in India's electoral jurisprudence, reinforcing the voter's right to information and contributing substantially to the project of electoral reform and democratic accountability.

The "NOTA judgment" refers to the decision of the Supreme Court of India in *People's Union for Civil Liberties v. Union of India*, which recognized the inclusion of the "None of the Above" (NOTA) option in Indian elections. The case originated from a public interest litigation filed by the People's Union for Civil Liberties, which argued that the right to vote encompasses not only the ability to choose among candidates but also the right to reject all candidates when none are deemed suitable. The petitioners contended that introducing NOTA would enhance voter autonomy and strengthen democratic accountability by allowing citizens to register principled dissent. Accepting this reasoning, the Court held that providing a NOTA option would advance the values of transparency, integrity, and participatory democracy by encouraging more informed and conscientious voter engagement. Although NOTA does not invalidate electoral outcomes, it functions as an institutional mechanism for expressing voter disapproval and for signalling to political parties the need for greater responsiveness, thereby contributing to the broader objective of ensuring free and fair elections and strengthening the freedom of expression of the electorate.

In *Lily Thomas v. Union of India*, the Supreme Court of India declared Section 8(4) of the Representation of the People Act, 1951 unconstitutional. Section 8 of the Act provides for disqualification upon conviction for specified offences, stipulating under sub-sections (1), (2), and (3) that a person convicted and sentenced to imprisonment shall stand disqualified from the date of conviction and remain so for a further period of six years following release. However, Section 8(4) created an exception for sitting Members of Parliament and State Legislatures, permitting them to retain their seats if they filed an appeal within three months of conviction, thereby deferring disqualification until the appeal was decided. The Court held that this differential treatment between elected representatives and other candidates violated constitutional principles, as it allowed convicted legislators to continue in office despite being otherwise disqualified from contesting elections. By striking down Section 8(4), the Court reinforced the norm of immediate disqualification upon conviction and underscored the imperative of maintaining probity and equality in the electoral and legislative process.

The case arose as a civil appeal challenging a decision of the Delhi High Court, wherein the petitioner, Subramanian Swamy, sought the issuance of a writ of mandamus directing the Election Commission of India to incorporate a "paper trail" mechanism in Electronic Voting Machines (EVMs). In *Subramanian Swamy v. Election Commission of India*, the Supreme Court of India held that a verifiable paper trail constitutes an indispensable component of free and fair elections, as it enhances transparency and public confidence in the electoral process. The Court endorsed the introduction of the Voter Verifiable Paper Audit Trail (VVPAT) system as an effective means of ensuring such transparency. Acknowledging the logistical and financial challenges involved, the Court recommended that the implementation of VVPAT be undertaken in a phased or geographically staggered manner, beginning with the 2014 General Elections. It further directed the Government of India to extend the necessary financial assistance to facilitate the procurement and deployment of VVPAT units. Further bulk of these judicial interventions have significantly

influenced the evolution of electoral reforms by safeguarding democratic values and ensuring that electoral processes remain fair, informed, and accountable.

Law Commission Reports on electoral reforms

The Law Commission of India has played a pivotal role in shaping the discourse on electoral reforms through several comprehensive reports addressing structural, legal, and ethical dimensions of India's electoral system. Notably, the 170th Report recommended measures such as the decriminalization of politics, regulation of political party finances, internal party democracy, and proportional representation in certain contexts. The 244th Report focused specifically proposing the disqualification of candidates against whom charges have been framed for serious offences, subject to safeguards against misuse. The 255th Report consolidated earlier suggestions and emphasized transparency in political funding, strengthening of the Model Code of Conduct, curbing paid news, and regulating opinion polls. Across these reports, the Commission consistently underscored the need to amend the Representation of the People Act, 1951 and related statutes to ensure greater accountability, fairness, and integrity in elections. Collectively, the Law Commission's recommendations have significantly influenced judicial pronouncements, legislative debates, and policy discussions, even though many proposals await full legislative implementation.

Election commission's initiative

The quality of elections is largely dependent on the quality of incumbents of the Election Commission. The Election Commission of India has undertaken a wide range of initiatives to advance electoral reforms aimed at enhancing transparency, inclusiveness, efficiency, and credibility in India's democratic process. Through administrative innovation, the Commission introduced Electronic Voting Machines and later VVPAT systems to reduce malpractice and improve voter confidence, while large-scale voter awareness campaigns such as Systematic Voters' Education and Electoral Participation (SVEEP) have sought to increase participation among women, youth, and marginalized groups. It has also implemented continuous updation and digitization of electoral rolls through the National Voters' Service Portal, introduced photo electoral rolls and Elector Photo Identity Cards to prevent impersonation, and tightened scrutiny of candidate nominations and campaign expenditure through real-time monitoring, flying squads, and expenditure observers. By enforcing the Model Code of Conduct during elections, regulating opinion polls and paid news, promoting accessible polling stations for persons with disabilities, and experimenting with remote voting technologies for migrant voters, the Commission has attempted to modernize electoral administration while maintaining fairness. Additionally, it has repeatedly recommended legal reforms to the Government of India on issues such as decriminalization of politics, inner-party democracy, simultaneous elections, and stricter regulation of political funding. Collectively, these initiatives demonstrate the Commission's proactive institutional role in strengthening the integrity and inclusiveness of India's electoral system.

Need of further reforms

Despite significant progress, several crucial electoral reforms remain necessary to strengthen the integrity and inclusiveness of India's democratic process. First, comprehensive regulation of political finance is essential, including transparent disclosure of donations, realistic expenditure limits, and state funding of recognized parties to reduce dependence on opaque funding channels. Despite having an unequivocal ban on overspending on elections, its infraction has become the norm. Legal proceedings to challenge violation of the law prohibiting excessive spending have exposed certain vulnerabilities of the law and institutions handling the law. Second, the criminalization of the political system in India has been widely acknowledged by numerous committees and expert bodies examining issues of political and electoral reform. This phenomenon manifests in several forms; however, one of the most alarming aspects is the growing presence of elected representatives who face serious criminal charges. The increasing number of legislators with pending criminal cases raises serious concerns regarding the integrity of democratic institutions and the quality of political leadership. Stronger measures are needed to address the criminalization of politics through speedy trials for candidates with serious charges, stricter disqualification norms, and greater accountability within political parties. Third, internal party democracy should

be institutionalized by mandating transparent candidate selection, regular organizational elections, and financial audits under the supervision of the Election Commission of India. Fourth, improving voter inclusion through remote voting options for migrant workers, easier registration procedures, and expanded accessibility for persons with disabilities would deepen participatory democracy. Fifth, electoral administration could benefit from technological safeguards such as secure digital campaign monitoring, enhanced cybersecurity for EVM-VVPAT systems, and regulation of social media misinformation. Sixth, there is widespread agreement that vote buying reduces the quality of democracy. Central to democracy is the participation and influence of voters in making collective decisions and solving collective problems. Vote selling and buying should be strictly curbed. Seventh, the Indian electorate, to a considerable extent, remains insufficiently aware of the potential risks associated with large-scale data aggregation and its capacity to influence public opinion. The convergence of conventional media and digital platforms, when combined with sophisticated data analytics, has increasingly enabled powerful political and economic actors to shape public discourse and voter perceptions in subtle yet significant ways. In this context, sections of the news media have also been criticized for sidelining critical issues, such as unethical practices involving influential business and political interests, while redirecting public debate toward comparatively less consequential matters. Such tendencies raise concerns regarding the role of the media, often described as the fourth pillar of democracy, in safeguarding transparency and accountability. When this institutional check weakens, it may inadvertently facilitate the functioning of a nexus among political leaders, business interests, and segments of the bureaucracy, thereby undermining democratic norms and informed electoral participation. A clear and well-defined regulatory protocols should be established and uniformly enforced for political broadcasting across the spectrum of media platforms. Such guidelines are essential to ensure fairness, transparency, and impartiality in the dissemination of political content during electoral periods. Effective oversight of political communication through broadcast and digital media can help prevent undue influence, misinformation, and unequal access to media space, thereby safeguarding the integrity of the democratic process. Finally, legal reforms through amendments to the Representation of the People Act, 1951 and clearer guidelines from the Supreme Court of India are necessary to ensure timely adjudication of election disputes, stronger enforcement of the Model Code of Conduct, and greater transparency in governance. Together, these reforms would help build a more accountable, equitable, and credible electoral system capable of sustaining the democratic ideals of the Constitution of India.

Conclusion

Many democracies that evolved through the intellectual currents of the Western Enlightenment have nevertheless developed institutional arrangements that often concentrate power within select elites. In India, institutions such as the Election Commission of India, the Supreme Court of India, and a vigilant civil society have consistently sought to curb electoral malpractices and strengthen democratic functioning through the conduct of free and fair elections. These bodies have introduced improved regulatory frameworks and adopted advanced technological measures to preserve the credibility of India's electoral process. Yet, the ultimate success of electoral reforms depends substantially on the willingness of political parties to comply with and internalize reform measures. Equally indispensable are an independent media and an informed public opinion capable of holding political actors accountable. When voters exercise their franchise conscientiously and penalize those who violate electoral norms, corrupt practices are likely to diminish, thereby enabling democracy to consolidate and realize its full potential.

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 1. *The superintendence, direction and control of the preparation of the electoral rolls for, and the conduct of, all elections to Parliament and to the Legislature of every State and of elections to the offices of President and Vice-President held under this Constitution shall be vested in a Commission (referred to in this Constitution as the Election Commission).*
 2. *The Election Commission shall consist of the Chief Election Commissioner and such number of other Election Commissioners, if any, as the President may from time-to-time fix and the appointment of the Chief Election Commissioner and other Election Commissioners shall, subject to the*

- provisions of any law made in that behalf by Parliament, be made by the President.
3. When any other Election Commissioner is so appointed the Chief Election Commissioner shall act as the Chairman of the Election Commission.
 4. Before each general election to the House of the People and to the Legislative Assembly of each State, and before the first general election and thereafter before each biennial election to the Legislative Council of each State having such Council, the President may also appoint after consultation with the Election Commission such Regional Commissioners as he may consider necessary to assist the Election Commission in the performance of the functions conferred on the Commission by clause (1).
 5. Subject to the provisions of any law made by Parliament, the conditions of service and tenure of office of the Election Commissioners and the Regional Commissioners shall be such as the President may by rule determine: Provided that the Chief Election Commissioner shall not be removed from his office except in like manner and on the like grounds as a Judge of the Supreme Court and the conditions of service of the Chief Election Commissioner shall not be varied to his disadvantage after his appointment: Provided further that any other Election Commissioner or a Regional Commissioner shall not be removed from office except on the recommendation of the Chief Election Commissioner.
 6. The President, or the Governor of a State, shall, when so requested by the Election Commission, make available to the Election Commission or to a Regional Commissioner such staff as may be necessary for the discharge of the functions conferred on the Election Commission by clause (1).
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